

A FAULT-TOLERANT HIERARCHICAL BROADCAST NETWORK

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Abstract

Hierarchical star or rooted tree networks have been implemented and have many desirable characteristics, including excellent performance, conceptual simplicity, and suitability for optical fiber implementations. They do, however, have a single point of vulnerability to catastrophic failure (the master or root hub) as well as vulnerabilities to single failures of links or hubs high in the hierarchy, which could disable large portions of the network. Hierarchical networks are first described, and their performance is compared to other local network alternatives. A generalization of the hub and network structure is then presented, which adds redundant network components to eliminate this vulnerability and make an extremely robust and fault-tolerant network.

Introduction

Hierarchical or tree broadcast networks offer a number of advantages, including simple station design, the ability to accommodate very many stations and long links to remote stations, and excellent performance over a wide range of loads. Moreover such networks can be built by the repetition of identical hubs, and new stations or hubs inserted as needed, with automatic network reconfiguration or reinitialization. Finally, they use only point-to-point links and are therefore suitable for fiber optic links with current fiber technology. Closs and Lee of IBM's Zurich research laboratory^{1,2} and Lee and Boulton³ of the University of Toronto have designed such networks and published reports on them. The Lee and Boulton effort has resulted in a commercial 50 Mbit/s network product. Such networks, however, do have a catastrophic single point of failure, the master or root hub. This paper first summarizes the basic concepts and features of hierarchical networks and compares their performance with alternative local networks. A means for introducing redundancy into such networks to provide very robust networks with a high degree of tolerance to faults in hubs or in individual data links is then described.

The Hierarchical Star Hub and Network

This paper roughly follows the terminology of Closs and Lee. Figure 1 illustrates the basic hierarchical network hub. Each hub has a "parent" side and a "child" side. On the parent side, there is one "up-link" to a parent hub and one "down-link." The hub may have any number of "children," each connected via up and down-links. Whatever is received on the parent

down-link is rebroadcast on all the children down-links. Whenever a packet begins on a child up-link, it contends against other child up-links, and, if no other up-link has already "captured" the "up-side" of the hub, may capture the hub. That packet is then sent on the up-link to the parent. It is important to understand that packets from children contend only at the instant they begin.

Figure 1. Hub Repeater

The hubs are interconnected as shown in figure 2. The key to network operation is the "root" or "master" hub at the top of the hierarchy. Its parent up-link is fed back into its parent down-link. Whichever child up-link captures the up-side of the master is fed back to the down side, and from there to every down-link in the network. Thus, the packet which captures the master is broadcast to every station in the network.

Lee and Boulton use a somewhat different terminology to describe a similar network. They split the tree at the root or master hub and show the interconnected up-sides as a "selection tree" and the interconnection down-sides as a "broadcast tree." Figure 3 shows the network of figure 2 depicted using the notation of Lee and Boulton.

Figure 2. Hierarchical Network

Figure 3. Alternate Presentation of Network in Fig. 2

However depicted, hierarchical star or rooted tree networks can be thought of as CSMA-CD networks with a nearly zero "destructive collision-window." Closs and Lee have implemented hubs where the arrival of two packets at a hub at exactly the same instant does cause a mutually destructive collision; the hub then recognizes this collision and stops sending both packets on its parent up-link. The collision-window is very small, only a few nanoseconds, determined by internal hub propagation and switching delays. Lee and Boulton have designed hubs which have no collision-window; that is, the hub always picks a clean winner, even when the two packets arrive exactly together.

Another way of looking at the hierarchical star network is to view it as an ALOHA network where one packet is guaranteed (or nearly guaranteed) to get through. In fact, Closs and Lee and Lee and Boulton have stations practice what amounts to an ALOHA protocol; whenever they have a message to send, they start sending it, without concern for whether the network is idle or active. The station then "listens" to see if it "hears" its packet on its down-link. If not, it tries again and so on until it succeeds in capturing the network. A station knows that what it receives, every station receives, so if it received its own packet, so did the whole network.

This causes more or less statistically random arbitration of the network (actually stations nearer the master hub have an advantage). In this sense, it is "fair," but it does not guarantee some fixed bandwidth allocation, nor any maximum delay to a station, everything is a matter of chance. Stations obviously can follow other protocols with hierarchical star networks. If all stations delay a fixed, cumulative interval of network-idle-time after successfully transmitting a packet, before sending another, then round-robin scheduling can be achieved with a heavily loaded network, and guaranteed bandwidth or access time allocations are possible.

Hierarchical star networks may employ a central-clock which originates at the master hub or can use independent clocks which originate at each station. Centrally clocked networks will have somewhat simpler stations, but more complex hubs and should have better performance for short messages. Independently clocked stations result in simpler hubs, but a bit synchronizing "preamble" must precede each packet, increasing per-packet overhead. The Lee and Boulton network is centrally clocked, while Closs and Lee describe a network with independent clocks at each station.

Performance

The performance of local networks is a complex subject, and fair, useful, direct comparisons of the characteristics of different networks are not easy. Nevertheless it is fairly easy to show that hierarchical star networks have excellent performance characteristics, which are demonstrably better in many respects than common alternative networks^{3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11}. This is because arbitration is fast (it takes a round-trip delay from the nearest station to the master hub wishing to transmit), arbitration delays are independent of the number of stations, and there is always (or nearly always) a clean winner from among contending packets.

The arbitration delay in token passing networks, rings, or broadcast buses, goes up linearly with the number of stations, if load is held constant. This is due to the need to pass the token through more stations. They are then, a poor choice for "sparse" networks; that is, networks with many stations but characteristically light loads. Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Detection (CSMA-CD) networks, such as

Ethernet* work very well for sparse situations, but suffer from the effects of collisions at high loads, which limit throughput and cause unpredictable access delays. As compared to CSMA/CD networks, Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA-CA) networks, such as HYPERchannel* or CI*¹⁹, sacrifice some extra delay at light loads for extra throughput at high loads. Like token passing networks, however, arbitration delay increases with the number of stations.

Both sparse and heavily loaded networks are of interest, and, of course, even networks which are normally lightly loaded may experience peak loads where they are heavily loaded. Delay matters comparatively little in some applications, but it is critical in others, particularly if the network connects processors to fast storage devices, or if the network is used for real time process control. Hierarchical star networks have the considerable virtue that they exhibit nearly ideal characteristics in both the sparse and heavily loaded cases. Lee and Boulton calculate the performance of their network and show that it behaves well under a variety of loads, including impulse loads which momentarily exceed network capacity³. They also show that, as with other types of networks, it is often higher level protocols, rather than network arbitration protocols, which limit perceived network performance.

Failures Modes and Reliability

Of the network types discussed above, CSMA/CD, CSMA/CA, token ring, token broadcast, and hierarchical star, CSMA/CA is probably inherently the most reliable since it can use a passive interconnection medium and has no analog collision detection problems. Passive failures of stations in CSMA/CA networks are harmless. Several schemes, including attenuating taps, are available to protect CSMA/CA networks from open or shortened "drop" cables.

CSMA/CD networks have tricky analog problems, if analog collision detection is employed. This can make even comparatively minor cable discontinuities produce apparent collisions, and the cable itself the weakness in these networks. CSMA/CD networks, which use two channels, one in and one out, do not have similar cable problems but typically do have a "head-end" or star repeater which is a single, active catastrophic failure point. Like CSMA/CA networks, passively failed or powered-off ports cause no problems.

The weakness of all Token Passing networks, ring or broadcast, is that every station in the token loop must actively pass the token on or respond to it. Procedures for recovering from lost or duplicate tokens considerably complicate these networks, and their failure analysis. Certainly protocol errors and recovery from them is a bigger concern with token passing networks than other kinds of networks considered here. Moreover, physical rings have an inherent catastrophic vulnerability to failures of any component in the ring: driver, receiver, cable, or station logic. Every component and every station must actively pass (or

remove) every packet without error or failure, or the effects are catastrophic. Bypass relays, counter-rotating dual rings, battery power back-up, distribution of interface power with the ring, and central wire-closets are all "band-aids" which can be applied to improve the reliability or availability of physical rings^{12,13,14,15,16,17,18}. Of these, central wire closets are the most complete solution, but they introduce considerable extra cable, and (at least for fiber optic links) they double the required number of drivers, receivers, and connectors, while they are themselves a point of catastrophic failure (better one point than many!). When all is said and done, there is little doubt that rings can be built to a high standard of reliability and availability, if one is willing to pay the price for redundancy or wire-centers.

Closs and Lee hierarchical star networks, like other non-token broadcast networks, are immune to catastrophic failure caused by passively failed stations. By putting a packet timer in the hubs, it is also easy to detect and disable continuously jabbering stations, a catastrophic failure mode for broadcast networks with entirely passive interconnections. The master hub, however, is an active single point of catastrophic failure, and the failure of any hub affects all subordinate stations. Link failures high in the hierarchy can also disable large parts of the network.

Closs and Lee have implemented a partial solution to the failed hub or link problem. Whenever a packet passes up from a hub to its parent, something (not necessarily the packet going up) should come down within a round-trip delay to the master hub. If not, the hub assumes a failed parent (or link to the parent) and reconfigures to loop back itself and become a master for all its children. If the master hub has n children, then after its failure there are n autonomous subnetworks.

Stations on each subnetwork can communicate to others in that same subnetwork, but not to any other subnetwork which must be reached through the master hub.

Fault-Tolerant Hierarchical Star Networks

Although hierarchical star networks are surely as reliable as most other local network approaches, they can become highly fault-tolerant, with minor modification and the introduction of some redundancy. They can, in fact, be made immune to catastrophic network failures caused by the failure any n hubs or links. Fault-tolerant, redundant hierarchical star networks should be suitable for critical networks where continued operation is vital, even in the face of significant damage. Such applications would include battlefield and shipboard Command, Control, Communications, and Intelligence (C³I) networks, where the network should continue in operation despite extensive battle damage, and many industrial applications. After all, one particularly wants a network controlling or monitoring an oil refinery to remain in operation, immediately after an explosion or during a fire. Moreover, many applications might profit from a broadcast network which requires several separate acts of sabotage before catastrophic failure occurs.

*Ethernet - Tm Xerox Corp.
HYPERchannel - Tm Network Systems Corp.
CI - Tm Digital Equipment Corp.

To introduce redundancy and fault-tolerance into the hierarchical networks, a generalization of the hub is first required. The hubs described previously provide for only one parent, but, if they are made a little more symmetrical, the hubs can have several parents (two is usually enough). Figure 4 illustrates such a hub. The "up-side" is now the mirror image of the down-side. X children are connected through the hub to Y parents. When the up-side is free, the first child up-link to start a new packet "captures" the up-side and that packet is transmitted on all up-links to parents. When the down-side is free, the first parent down-link to start a new packet captures the down-side, and is transmitted on all child down-links.

Figure 4. Modified Hub Repeater

Figure 5 illustrates the network of figure 2 with the addition of an alternate master hub (hub 14) and redundant links to that hub. Each child hub is now connected directly, or indirectly, to both the master and alternate master hubs. The alternate master is also a child of the master hub, but its second parent link is looped back on itself, through a delay line.

If optical fiber were used, the delay line could just be a coil of fiber; if an electrical transmission medium were used in the network, a shift register delay line could be used. The delay line must have a delay longer than the round trip from the alternate master to the master and back (actually, as we shall see, it needs somewhat more than this, to handle some particular failures).

Figure 5. Fault-Tolerant Network

Figure 6 illustrates the same network after total failure of the master hub. Now the alternate master (hub 14) acts as master. There is some extra delay, due to the delay line and longer paths to the alternate master, but complete interconnection is maintained.

Figure 6. Network After Failure of Master Hub

Figure 7 illustrates the failure of the link from hub 2 to the master. Packets from the children of hub 2 now pass through the alternate master to the master, and connectivity is maintained. Figure 8 illustrates one of the trickiest failures, the failure of the link between the master and alternate master hubs. This is the worst case for the alternate master delay line. Enough delay is required so that the round trips from either hub 2 or hub 3, through the alternate master and back, is longer than the round trip from hub 2 or hub 3 through the master hub and back. If this rule were not followed, different packets might be received by stations attached to different hubs.

Figure 7. Network After Failure of One Link

Figure 8. Network After Failure of Alternate Master to Master Hub Link

Another rule is required for "Asynchronous" versions (that is networks with no central clock) of the network. The minimum packet size must take longer to transmit than the greatest difference in one-way propagation delay between the shortest path and the longest path from any station to the master hub. This rule is necessary to prevent the network from generating duplicate copies of short packets.

"Synchronous" versions (networks where the master hub generates a central clock) would be slightly different. The master hub would generate a stream of "synch" characters when the network was idle. Stations would return this synchronizing stream to hubs, which would return it to the master. To send a packet, a station would maintain the received clock, but send up a unique

starting delimiter, the packet and ending delimiter. On the up-side, packets would capture hubs in a manner directly analogous to the asynchronous case. On the down-sides, however, there would be a built-in link priority, and the highest priority link would always "capture" and hold the hub as long as either idle characters or a message were present.

Synchronous versions have advantages and disadvantages. No special bit synchronizing preamble need be appended to packets, as with the asynchronous case. This makes short packets more efficient than in the asynchronous case. Also, there is no minimum packet size constraint. Stations might be a little simpler, and would not require precise crystal oscillators. On the other hand, hubs would be more complex; in particular, a phase lock oscillator and a small FIFO would be required for each link. Logic to recognize starting and ending delimiters would also be needed.

Summary of Advantages

Redundant hierarchical star networks have the following advantages:

- Since only point-to-point connections are used, they are suitable for fiber optics.
- The entire network can be made by repetition of a single kind of simple hub.
- The hubs have a very regular structure and are made by repetitions of simple elements, thus are very easily implemented in various kinds of LSI including programmable arrays, semicustom, and fully custom logic.
- The simple, regular structure facilitates testing of chips and hubs.
- The network can be made as reliable as desired, and can be made virtually immune to failure or damage of hubs or cables.
- Arbitration delay and overhead are small and independent of the number of stations.
- Since arbitration is centralized in the network, individual stations are simplified (somewhat as compared to other broadcast networks, and greatly as compared to rings). There are more stations than hubs in the network.
- Protocols are very simple and automatically handle failures.
- Different transmission media are easily mixed in the same network.
- A station can be any distance from the master hub. Very remote stations will, however, have a lower effective network priority.

As compared to CSMA-CD networks, redundant hierarchical stars have the following advantages:

- Collisions do not reduce effective network utilization even under heavy loads.

- Electrical installation and wiring is much less tricky than single cable CSMA-CD networks, since there are no analog collision detection problems, nor taps to bussed cables.
- Ports can be simpler than those which do collision detection by comparison of transmitted and received messages.
- With appropriate station protocols, worst case network access delays can be bounded.
- Damaged cables are nearly harmless in redundant hierarchical star networks, but generally are catastrophic in single cable CSMA-CD networks.

As compared to rings, redundant hierarchical star networks have the following advantages:

- Protocols are much simpler, particularly when fault recovery is considered.
- Hubs and stations are far simpler than stations for reasonably reliable rings, which should reduce their expense and make them far easier to test (consider the problem of verifying that every station for a counter-rotating token ring correctly handles all error conditions).
- Delay is not increased simply by adding stations, though, of course, adding load will increase average packet delays.
- The hierarchical star network, even without redundancy, is much more reliable than simple rings without elaborate, complex protection features (e.g., counter-rotating rings, station bypasses, and central wiring concentrator/bypasses).

The major disadvantage to redundant hierarchical star networks is simply that they use a larger number of cables, drivers, receivers, and connectors than some other network approaches. They, however, have only slightly or no more cables, etc., than reliable rings (e.g., counter-rotating rings, or electrically switched star/rings).

Conclusion

Redundant hierarchical star networks are an attractive local network alternative, suitable for fiber optics, with excellent performance and reliability characteristics. Stations are simplified and performance is improved by moving arbitration from the station to the active network elements. The active network elements (hub repeaters) have a simple, regular structure which makes them unusually well suited for large scale integration and easy to test; therefore, they should be quite inexpensive.

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